

AN INNOVATIVE HARVESTING SYSTEM FOR MULTIPURPOSE HEMP

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ABSTRACT: The industrial hemp (*Canapa sativa* L.) is a crop cultivated for multiple uses; the products are obtained from different plant parts such as seeds, leaves, and stem. From an agronomical point of view, some problems remain for the cultivation of hemp especially on the selection of stable varieties and on gaps in harvesting technologies, which impede the full exploitation of the species. This study aimed at testing the performance of a new machine used for the combined harvesting of hemp seeds and fibers. In particular, machine productivity and work quality were assessed in a field test respect a specific timeframe. Results indicated interesting performances, with good productivity and good work quality, basically in line with the performance of other combines used in other common crops.

Keyword: hemp, harvesting, combine, seeds, fiber.

1. INTRODUCTION

The industrial hemp (*Canapa sativa* L.) is a multipurpose annual herbaceous plant with erect stem reaching over 4 meters in height. It grows best in zones with temperate climate (13-22° C), but will also thrive in higher or lower climates. It is suitable for cultivation in temperate zones, in the Mediterranean and in the sub-tropics [1].

After a period of declining interest, the cultivation of hemp is back to being considered profitable in Europe. In particular, hemp is appreciated because of the multiple uses that derive from the different plant parts, i.e seeds, leaves, and stem. Currently, all aboveground biomass of hemp can be exploited in determined processing facilities and using specific technologies.

The most important product obtained from the plant is the fiber, consisting in sclerenchyma fibers associated to the phloem of the plant (bast fiber). They arise with primary tissues from the apical meristem, or with secondary tissues produced by the lateral meristem, the cambium, associated with the vascular tissues of the stem [2]. Recently, the bast fibers gained importance also as renewable feedstock for the production of strong, lightweight composite material, offering several advantages as replacement for fiber glass [3, 4]. Nowadays, the application of natural fiber composites are found in automotive interiors, agricultural and automotive exterior panels, acoustic and thermal insulation, furniture, recreational sport products such as tennis racquets, skateboards, bike frames, marine products, and construction materials [5].

Bast fibers are extracted through decortications processes which involve the use of specialized machine. The residues of the fiber processing consist in dust and shives, the latter is used successfully by the green building enterprise, while the dust can be composted and used as fertilizer.

Another very important product obtained from hemp is the seed. Hemp seeds can be used for producing derivatives such as edible oil or flour. The nutritional and healthy properties of the hemp seeds make the derivatives very appreciated by consumers and very researched in the elite-food market [6].

Finally, among the hemp products, great importance is assumed by the residues of seeds threshing, mainly composed by leaves and floral residues. This material is in great demand by pharmaceutical and chemical industries for the preparation of CBD-based products.

However, the success of the hemp products is not yet in line with the success of its cultivation. From an

agronomical point of view, some problems remain on the selection of stable varieties and on technological gaps in harvesting technologies, which impede the full exploitation of the species and the wide spread of its cultivation. In fact, the morphological characteristics of this plant make difficult the mechanical harvest and in most cases, the harvesting systems are developed locally, based on available solutions in connection with specific local agricultural practice [7].

Nevertheless, in the last years some progresses have been made in respect of harvesting technology innovations. In this paper are reported the results of a harvesting test made in Romania in September 2015 with a combine equipped with a double head designed for the harvest of hemp seeds and fibers. Since 2015, the system is brought to the market commercially in a cooperation between HempFlax and John Deere dealer Groenoord BV. The system is available as an adaptation to current line of John Deere W type combine series (figure 1).

The test was performed within the objective of the Italian project SUSACE and the EU project FIBRA, in which the CREA-ING and HempFlax have collaborated for the identification of suitable harvesting technologies of bast fiber crops in Europe and China.

Figure 1: lateral view of the combine John Deere W660 equipped with the system “double cut”.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The trial took place in a rectangular land portion having a surface of 1,99 ha (GPS coordinate 45°55'0"N and 23°32'59"E). The land is property of the company HempFlax and is included in the territory of the Petrești (250 a.s.l.), near Alba Iulia, Transilvania region, Romania.

The soil preparation was performed by HempFlax and consisted in a medium depth plowing, followed by harrowing and sowing. In first place, the fertilization applied consisted of 500 kg of NPK 15/15/15 per ha, successively corroborated with 140 kg N33% per ha. Sowing was performed in mid April 2015 using 35 kg of seeds variety Felina per ha.

The modified combine is a mod. *John Deere W660* (270 kW power), equipped with a wheat-head mod. *John Deere 613R* in the upper part and a Kemper-type head mod. *John Deere 445* in the lower part.

The upper header provides the cut of the upper part of the stalks (40-50 cm) including the seeds. The lower header cut the remaining stalks in pieces of 60-70 cm length with the Hempcut technology. In this system, only the upper part is going through the combine harvester, so the volume of biomass to be threshed through the machine is tremendously reduced compared to other machines used for the same purpose in the past. The threshed seeds are collected in a hopper of the machine and at full charge can be successively unloaded in a trailer. The cut stem portions are unloaded posteriorly in a windrow about 1 m wide (figure 2).

Figure 2: combine during harvest operation; in the lower part of the photo it is visible the windrow of stem portions left in the field after the passage of the machine.

The main characteristics of the crops have been identified through 5 experimental plots of 1 m² randomly selected in the field test. The measured field parameters were the following: mean plant density per m², mean plant height, mean diameter of the stalk, mean length of the panicles, mean weight of the total biomass per plot.

The seed yield per ha was calculated by direct weighing of the seeds collected in the entire field test through a certified weighing machine, while the biomass yield per ha was estimated on the base of the measurements obtained from the experimental plots.

The working times were evaluated according to ASABE standard methods (ASABE Standards 2006 and ASAE Standards 2000). Other references include the Commission Internationale de l'Organisation Scientifique du Travail en Agriculture (CIOSTA) and the Italian Society of Agricultural Engineering (AIIA) 3A R1. A reference to these methods can be found in Bodria et al. 2006.

From the crossing of the data obtained it was possible to determine the following parameters: effective field capacity (ha/h), operative field capacity (ha/h), machine yield respect seeds and biomass production (tons/h).

In order to evaluate the work quality, other parameters such as mean cutting height, mean height of the windrow, mean width of the windrow, and mean length of the stem portions were measured on the base of 30 measurements per each parameter.

3. RESULTS

In Table I are shown the data concerning the crop characteristics

Table I: crop characteristic

Crop characteristics	Unit	Value
Plant density	plants/m ²	99 ± 18
Mean plant height	cm	202 ± 2
Mean diameter	mm	8,57 ± 1,6
Mean length of the panicle	cm	29,4 ± 11
Mean weight of the biomass per plot	Kg/m ²	2,3 ± 2

The disregarded result identified in the plots was the mean height of the plants, because industrial hemp is known to exceed 3 m in height quite easily. Probably, according to the farmer, the scarce growing was due to the high temperatures of the summer, significantly above the mean of the year. However, specific meteorological data of the area are missing.

The data of the crop productivity are shown in Table II.

Table II: crop productivity data

Data of crop productivity (fresh basis)	Unit	Value
Total biomass	ton/ha	23 ± 2,9
* stem and threshing residues	ton/ha	22,2 ± 2,9
* seeds	ton/ha	0,78
Moisture content of the biomass	%	40
Moisture content of the seeds	%	25

In general the data obtained can be considered satisfactory and in line with the yield identified in the literature [8]. It must be pointed out that results are expressed on fresh basis, so the effective yield of pure and dry seeds will be lower of about 15% respect the parameter identified, while the yield in fiber will correspond to about 6/7 tons/ha.

In Table III are indicated the data concerning the performance of the machine and obtained crossing the study of the working times with the data of crop productivity.

Table III: data concerning machine productivity

* f.b. = fresh basis

Machine performance	Unit	Value
Effective velocity	m/s	1,72
Operative velocity	m/s	1,37
Effective field capacity	ha/h	2,48
Operative field capacity	ha/h	2,00
Hourly seed productivity	t/h (f.b.)*	1,56
Hourly biomass productivity	t/h (f.b.)*	44,4

These results must be interpreted taking into account mainly the operative capacity, i.e. the parameter that considers accessory times such as turnings, death times,

and unloading times. Indeed, the reference parameter of 2 ha/h can be considered in line with the performance of

Table IV: data concerning machine work quality

	Unit	Value
Mean cutting height	cm	19,5 ± 5,7
Mean windrow height	cm	39,6 ± 7,5
Mean windrow width	cm	104,2 ± 4,3
Mean length of the stem portions	cm	58,4 ± 9,2

other combines utilized for the harvesting of oil crops[9].

The post harvest data utilized to study the work quality of the machine are summarized in table IV.

4. CONCLUSION

The work presented aimed at testing an innovative system for the combined harvesting of industrial hemp. The machine has shown interesting performance in respect of both working times and work quality. At current, this type of solution represents undoubtedly one of the best options to exploit entirely the hemp products at industrial level. The limiting factor of this study was the scarce plant growth, as plant height is the main problem affecting mechanical harvest. Therefore, future tests in more representative plantations should be performed in order to fully validate the findings of this research.

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7. LOGO

Research projects SUSCACE and FIBRA

